

Bio Fibre EU Manufacturers

Initial list of European bio fibre manufacturers and contact information

This document provides an initial list of European bio fibre manufacturers identified by AMURA within the BioStruct project.

The purpose of this document is to compile basic manufacturer and contact information available at this stage, as a starting point for the identification of potential bio fibre sources relevant to the project.

The information listed in this document corresponds to the contact details available at the time of compilation.

No.	Company	Location	Website	Contact email
1	Bcomp	Switzerland	https://www.bcomp.com	thomas.klaus@bcomp.ch
2	Hexcel Fibers	Spain – France	https://www.hexcel.com	paula.constantinou@hexcel.com
3	Ecotechnilin	France	https://eco-technilin.com	contact@eco-technilin.com
4	Fibertech Group	Italy	https://fibertechgroup.it	info@fibertechgroup.it
5	Safilin	France	https://www.safilin.fr	adual@safilin.fr
6	Depestele Sart	France	https://groupepestele.com	sales@depestele.com
7	Saertex	France	https://www.saertex.com	l.becerra@saertex.com